

Art of Storytelling: A Study of R. K. Narayan's Short Stories and Their Reflection on Indian Culture

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Abstract

R.K Narayan is one of the most popular writers in the history of Indian English Literature. His short stories are representations of various cultural circumstances of contemporary Indian society. His characters not only represented various personalities but also inspired others in several ways. He has used various mythological concepts in his short stories to reflect Indian culture in various contexts. By incorporating Indian myths and legendary characters, Narayan portrays religious rituals as credible practices in the Indian context. This blending of myth and the real lives of common people adds depth and cultural context to his narratives. This paper explores the art of storytelling in R.K Narayan's short stories and their reflection on Indian cultural values. His stories are known for their vivid depiction of Indian culture and traditional customs. This paper is an attempt to analyze how Narayan uses his narrative techniques to represent various elements in Indian society, and also the role of women characters in his narratives. It also studies how his popular works reflect the social and cultural practices of our country during the period of independence. R.K. Narayan's short stories offer a multifaceted interpretation of Indian culture, reflecting its contradictions and convolutions. Hence, the findings of this study point out that the unique narrative technique of Narayan captures the essence of Indian culture making him a noteworthy figure in the contemporary era of Indian English Literature.

Keywords: Short Story, Narrative technique, Indian Culture, Society, Tradition, Reflections

Introduction

R.K Narayan is a well-known writer in the history of Indian English Literature known for his unique portrayal of Indian culture and the life of ordinary people. Rasipuram Krishnaswami Iyer Narayanaswami was RK Narayan's full name. He was an Indian author best known for his stories set in the fictional town of Malgudi in southern India. He was one of the pioneers of early Indian literature in English, alongside Mulk Raj Anand and Raja Rao. Narayan focuses on the upbringing and routine of his characters. He's been equated to William Faulkner, who created a similar fictional town and wrote about the strength of everyday life with intellect and compassion. For his ability to make complex plots simple, Narayan's work has drawn comparisons with Guy de Maupassant.

R.K. Narayan's short stories are a testament to the rich cultural values of our country, and their characters have a huge impact on the current Indian society. These stories have various elements that reflect the complexities and contradictions of Indian culture. Narayan's narratives play a vital role in Indian English Literature, providing an exceptional blending of realism and romanticism. His narrative pieces are known for their simple language, satirical elements and relatable cultural representations. His unique narrative style includes humanism, symbolism, sarcasm, and humour which create thought-provoking situations throughout the reading paths. This paper focuses on R.K. Narayan's short stories and their characters, examining how they reflect Indian culture and its conflicts. The eminent writer incorporates various threads of Indian culture such as myths, rituals, superstitions, and customs to weave the overall reflective attire of Indian culture in his short stories. The use of these poetic elements contributes to a unique style of narration in his works.

Most of the short stories written by R.K Narayan are set in the fictional town namely Malgudi, a miniature representation of Indian society. The small town is the representation of many places in India which consists of several characters, each representing different kinds of jobs and occupations. To establish a distinguishable Indian community in his novels, Narayan uses various human types, such as priests, clerks, criminals, guides and painters. Other human types include dancers and painters as well as hotel owners and tailors. Types are indeed generic, but in Narayan, the essential is notified by a peculiarity in uneasiness. Adding to the mythological feel of Malgudi, he named the river Sarayu and dotted the landscape with ruinous buildings as well as dense forests and mysterious ruins. Narayan is an original and truly Indian writer

because of his genuine and compassionate attitude toward people and the outside world, as well as the uniqueness and inventiveness of the characters he creates in his stories. The portrayal of characters in the stories and their interactions gives a lucid understanding of Indian culture and its complexities. The themes and motifs of these short stories include the conflict between various things in society such as traditional and modern cultural values, the role of women in the family and society, and the cultural variance between eastern and western countries. The analysis of these themes examines how the writer used these elements to reflect the cultural and social realities of our country during the period of freedom struggle. The renowned writer R.K Narayan contributes a significant part of Indian English Literature, by providing a unique perspective on the Indian cultural values and society. His narrative style offers a deep reflection of Indian culture through his portrayal of characters. The qualitative research approach uses a mixed methodology of literary analysis and cultural critique in order to explore the thematic elements of selected short stories. The study focuses on the analysis of Narayan's most popular short stories such as *A Horse and Two Goats* and *The Vendor of Sweets* that are part of *Malgudi Days*. These short stories highlight the themes of regionalism, humanism, symbolism, sarcasm, and irony through which the writer proves his unique narrative style. His narrative technique adds not only entertainment but also thought-provoking rudiments to his works. This study is an attempt to provide a comprehensive analysis of the art of storytelling in the short stories written by Narayan, the renowned writer, and their impact on Indian culture.

Reflection of Culture in *A Horse and Two Goats*

Indian culture is highly reflected in one of the most popular stories of R.K Narayan namely *A Horse and Two Goats*. This story mainly deals with themes such as cultural exchange, poverty, social inequity, and the conflicts between conventional and modern Indian society. It delineates the complexities of cultural diversity and the challenges of cross-cultural communication. The story has a poignant reflection of Indian society and culture, providing the best intuition into contemporary disputes about cultural identity and change in society. The story revolves around the protagonist Muni, a deprived villager who owns a red stone sculpture of a horse. An American tourist who wants to buy the sculpture makes the situation more hilarious because of the miscommunication between Muni and the tourist. The language barrier and the variant cultural backgrounds of the two men make their communication hard and unhealthy. The story of *A Horse and Two Goats* describes the struggles of poverty, cultural diversity and the clash between traditional and modern Indian society. Since contemporary India is globally moving

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forward and the prevalence of cultural exchange is gradually increasing, the story deals with a profound and thoughtful theme of cultural values.

Language Discrepancy is the central theme throughout the story in which the knowledge of the English language plays as a major parameter in the education system. According to the research study of Aakarsh,

“The colonial enterprise has the belief which is certainly colonized that the native language their suppression by the foreign languages is quite reasonable” (Aakarsh 2022).

In the second half of the twentieth century, Indians already accepted that the English language is a global language and the society and its culture began to imitate Western culture. The momentum of the English language started escalating to a higher level of attainability. Muni, the protagonist of the story does not panic about his lack of English proficiency rather he is scared of the English government authorities at that time. Through this character, the writer tries to bring up the idea of a good English education for the privileged people of Indian society. He also successfully amalgamates humour with the seriousness of linguistic and cultural conflicts in the story. The research study proves that,

“R.K Narayan establishes humour in the ironical, antithetical dialogism between the characters. ... Double discourse is established when the conversation ensues with a converging point” (Aakarsh 2022).

The story has a huge impact on the social status of the Indian common people. It reveals the tension between the traditional and modern cultural values of Indian society. Indian society has faced a drastic change in its culture and the Westernized perspective of culture creates a charming contract that reflects the various views on the cultural changes in India.

Representation of Indianness

The core part of Hinduism and its traditional customs become the major thread for weaving short stories by Narayan. There is a prominent aspect of Indianness in each of his short stories. The religious faith and religious environment have become the protuberant feature in his popular stories namely *Swami and Friends* and *The Vendor of Sweets*. In *Swami and Friends*, the protagonist protests about the criticism of Hindu Gods and religious customs. R.K Narayan tries to incorporate Hindu philosophy, its beliefs and its customs into most of his stories. The

protagonist of the short story *The Vendor of Sweets* is influenced by the Bhagavad Gita. With the frequent incorporation of myths, legendary notes and supernatural elements into the short stories, Narayan catches the interests of Western readers too. However, he enhances the authenticity of depicting Indian life in his stories with these magical elements of cultural and mythical values. These storytelling elements are deeply rooted in the Indian cultural consciousness of the writer.

The small fictional town namely Malgudi, which is the backdrop of most of his stories, is an intellectual creation of the writer based on his own hometown near Mysore in Karnataka. This plot in all the stories allows him to delineate the rhythms and customs of life of common people in India. R.K Narayan frequently brings out the mythical elements of the great epics Ramayana and Mahabharata in his short stories in order to offer depth and resonance to them. The short story *Naga* is one of the best examples of this concept as it draws upon the lore of a snake deity Naga from a Hindu mythological story. The myth of Naga, the snake deity is brought into the setting of a contemporary small town in India. The story revolves around the mysterious myth of the stone image that appears in a temple where the folks believe that it is a manifestation of Naga. This mythical element is used in the story in the motif of exploring the themes of faith, superstition and the complexities between traditional and modernity of Indian society. Mat McDermott in his article, opines that,

“The deepest single spiritual truth represented in the Vedas is that Brahman which refers to the Divine, pervades the whole universe. ... its preservation and dissolution and transformation are done in a complete repetition of a cycle” (McDermott 2016).

By using the rich tapestry of Hindu mythology, R.K Narayan proves his unique storytelling style which imbues the narrative technique with a sense of endurance and universal implication. Narayan examines the deepest philosophical and spiritual dimensions of the characters' lives through these implications in all his short stories.

India is known for its rich cultural values since ancient times and the civilization has been undergoing a drastic transformation throughout its history. India is one of the countries that have a rich heritage, religious festivals, cultural policies and so on. These cultural standards play a vital role in the formation of societal attitudes. They help the people keep unity among themselves, making them celebrate their lives with extreme happiness and harmony. The

portrayal of this harmony in Narayan's stories motivates the modern generation maintaining traditional cultural values. The studies of Jaydipkumar Pandya states that

“With the help of realistic imitation, Narayan has separated himself from social goals as an artist. ... His characters and community are kept in a good balance by him” (Pandya 2021).

Conclusion

R.K Narayan, one of the most renowned writers of Modern India, has intellectually undergone a masterful exploration of ancient Indian culture and its significant relation with the present Indian society. Narayan crafts stories that transcend the geographical boundaries of the fictional town Malgudi and his stories talk to the universal human understandings. His keen observation of the common Indian people makes him understand them empathetically and create innovative narratives that are universally appreciable. He tries to capture the everyday joys and sorrows, complexities of life and the multifaceted perspectives of the ordinary people in the society. The consistent charm of his narratives lies in their ability to take the readers into the richness of the country's cultural values resonating with the collective human experiences. R.K Narayan's art of storytelling has left an ineradicable mark on Indian English Literature and they inspire the upcoming young writers to explore more about the cultural identity. His legacy stands as an evidence of the transformative pathway of Indian literature, reminding the next generation that the art of storytelling is a vital channel to express the empathetical understanding of human emotions.

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